

See discussions, stats, and author profiles for this publication at: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/239533609>

Multiscale Texture Feature Variability Analysis in Images During Laparoscopy Under Different Viewing Positions

Conference Paper · April 2004

CITATIONS

6

READS

20

6 authors, including:

C. S. Pattichis

University of Cyprus

431 PUBLICATIONS 5,676 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

Marios S Pattichis

University of New Mexico

334 PUBLICATIONS 3,294 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

Efthymoulos C Kyriacou

Frederick University

174 PUBLICATIONS 2,441 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

Some of the authors of this publication are also working on these related projects:

mEducator [View project](#)

Deployment of Generic Cross-Boarder eHealth Services in Cyprus [View project](#)

Multiscale Texture Feature Variability Analysis in Images During Laparoscopy Under Different Viewing Positions

Neophytou S. Marios^{1,3}, Pattichis S. Constantinos¹, Pattichis S. Marios¹, Tanos Vasilios², Kyriacou C. Efthymoulos¹, Koutsouris Dimitris³

¹Department of Computer Science, University of Cyprus, Nicosia, Cyprus,
{[mneoph](mailto:mneoph@ucy.ac.cy), [pattichi](mailto:pattichi@ucy.ac.cy), [mariosp](mailto:mariosp@ucy.ac.cy), [ekyriac](mailto:ekyriac@ucy.ac.cy)} @ucy.ac.cy

²Evaggelistris Medical Center, Nicosia, Cyprus, tanosv@spidernet.com.cy

³Biomedical Engineering Laboratory, Department of Electrical and Computer Engineering, National Technical University of Athens, Greece, dkoutsou@biomed.ntua.gr

Abstract

In this study we investigate variability of texture features for laparoscopy images of tissue captured under different viewing conditions. In order to perform this test we captured the following sets of images: ten images, where the camera was at a small distance from the tissue (panoramic, 5cm distance), ten images where the camera was close to the tissue (close up, 3cm distance) and twenty images for two consecutive angles (ten for each) with 5° degrees difference. Multiscale analysis was carried out in order to examine image texture at different scales. Images were downsampled and filtered to ten scales (1x1 up to 10x10) for the different distances and six scales (1x1 up to 5x5 and 10x10) for the different angles. Regions of Interest (ROIs) were selected from each image and the following texture features were extracted: the Statistical Features (SF) and the Spatial Gray Level Dependence Matrices (SGLDM). Results indicate that there is significant variability between the panoramic and close up views for multiscale texture features. However, there is some variance (within reasonable bounds) between the multiscale texture features of consecutive angles. It is hoped that the results of this study will prove useful in computer aided diagnosis in laparoscopy imaging. However, more experiments have to be carried out and more images have to be analyzed to support this further.

1. Introduction

Laparoscopy has become the preferred method for diagnosis and treatment of the majority in gynaecological problems. Laparoscopy is minimally invasive technique due to the very small incisions used [1]. The eye piece of a 10mm in diameter telescope is connected to a camera and a monitor. The physician guides the telescope tip inside the abdominal cavity in order to investigate suspicious areas and to establish the diagnosis [2]. Many times the diagnosis is difficult and histopathological examination of a biopsy is necessary for conclusive results. Laparoscopic computer based image processing is a difficult task but we investigate the possibility of having an additional information of the suspected regions observed during laparoscopy before biopsy results. The main objective of this study is to investigate the differences of texture features of laparoscopy images under different viewing conditions using multiscale analysis.

To the best of our knowledge no similar study was performed for laparoscopy imaging. Similar work was presented only for colonoscopy images [3]-[4] for the detection of tumours in colonoscopic video where the performance in the detection rate of abnormal colonic regions corresponding to adenomatous polyps was very high. In previous work by our group we studied images from three different organs (endometrium, cervix and ovary) trying to compare normal and abnormal regions of interest. Only texture features were extracted and the results were very promising [5].

However, in order to investigate further the differences of laparoscopy imaging features when computed under different viewing conditions we decided to carry out this study using multiscale analysis in chicken.

2. Methodology

In order to capture the images the CIRCONE IP4.1 endoscopic camera was used. The analog output signal of the camera (PAL 475 horizontal lines) was digitised using the Matrox Meteor II frame grabber which was installed in a PC. Through this system the physician is able to select and freeze RGB images with a resolution of 720x576 pixels x24 bits (tiff format) and transform them to gray scale format in order to carry out the analysis. The following images were captured from the experimental tissue (chicken): i) ten panoramic images, at 5cm distance as illustrated in Fig. 1a, ii) ten close up images, at 3cm distance as illustrated in Fig. 1b, and iii) twenty images for two consecutive angles of 5 degrees difference. The physician manually selected Regions of Interest (ROI) as illustrated in Fig 1 on all images. Multiscale analysis and texture features were computed for the evaluation of the different capturing conditions.

2.1 Multiscale Analysis

The goal of multiscale image analysis is to reveal image characteristics at different image resolutions [6]. For example, small objects affect texture features at low resolution levels (with little or no downsampling involved), while larger objects affect texture features at higher resolution levels. Thus, if there is a particular range of scales, where we have objects of diagnostic interest, it is preferable to use this range for feature extraction in computer aided diagnostic systems. Within a single image scale, there is a number of different frequency bands that can be used for texture feature analysis. In this study, we used only the low-frequency band, where most of the image energy is nearly-always concentrated. This was implemented by first applying a low-pass filter, followed by downsampling by a factor of two to ten in each direction. Multiscale analysis was applied to all captured images using a scale from 1x1 to 10x10 in close up and panoramic views and 1x1 to 5x5 and 10x10 range to different angles views. Figure 2 illustrates the resampled images for panoramic and close up views for the scales 2x2 to 5x5. Texture features were then computed for the ROIs of the downsampled images.

2.2 Feature Extraction

Texture features were extracted from the ROIs using the following feature sets:

A. Statistical Features (SF): SF features describe the gray level histogram distribution without considering spatial independence. The following texture features were computed: 1) Mean value, 2) Variance, 3) Median value, 4) Skewness, 5) Kurtosis, 6) Energy, 7) Entropy and 8) Mode.

B. Spatial Gray Level Dependence Matrices (SGLDM): The spatial gray level dependence matrices as proposed by Haralick et al. [7] are based on the estimation of the second-order joint conditional probability density functions that two pixels (k,l) and (m,n) with distance d in direction specified by the angle θ , have intensities of gray level i and gray level j . Based on the probability density functions the following texture measures were computed: 1) Angular second moment, 2) Contrast, 3) Correlation, 4) Sum of squares: variance, 5) Inverse difference moment, 6) Sum average, 7) Sum variance, 8) Sum entropy, 9) Entropy, 10) Difference variance, 11) Difference entropy, 12) Homogeneity, and 13) Information measures of correlation. For a chosen distance d (in this work $d=1$ was used) and for angles $\theta = 0^\circ, 45^\circ, 90^\circ$ and 135° we computed four values for each of the above texture

measures. The above features were calculated for displacements $\delta=(0,1)$, $(1,1)$, $(1,0)$, $(1,-1)$, where $\delta\equiv(\Delta x,\Delta y)$, and their mean values were taken.

3. Results

The multiscale texture features ASM, contrast, variance and homogeneity for panoramic vs. close up views are tabulated in Table I for scales 1x1 to 10x10. As shown in Table I, for scale 3x3 all four features have significant difference between close up and panoramic views, whereas for scale 6x6 and 9x9 all four features have no significant difference. In the other scales, certain features have significant difference whereas others have not.

Figures 3 to 5 illustrate the multiscale analysis results for the first experiment (panoramic vs. close up view) for the texture features homogeneity, entropy, and correlation respectively.

Figure 1: Original gray scale image with ROI shown in square area with white perimeter. (a) Panoramic view and (b) Close up view.

Figure 2: ROI downsampled images. (a) - (d) Panoramic views, at scales 2x2 to 5x5 and (e) - (h) Close up views at 2x2 to 5x5

As illustrated in Fig. 3, the texture feature of homogeneity has a maximum value for 2x2 downsampling scale. Also, as illustrated in Fig. 4, the entropy feature drops at the same downsample scale (i.e. 2x2) and then it varies very little. According to this we can conclude that the optimum downsampling scale is 2x2 for this example.

TABLE I: SGLDM TEXTURE FEATURES (CLOSE UP - PANORAMIC) FOR ALL SCALES {Q₁, Q₃, AND SIQR REPRESENT THE LOWER QUANTILE (25% PERCENTILE), UPPER QUANTILE (75% PERCENTILE) AND THE SEMI-INTER QUANTILE RANGE, RESPECTIVELY}

Scale	Q ₁	Median	Q ₃	SIQR	Q ₁	Median	Q ₃	SIQR	H ¹
1x1	Close Up				Panoramic				H ¹
ASM ²	0,004	0,005	0,007	0,001	0,003	0,008	0,021	0,009	0
Contrast	73,754	82,989	93,377	9,811	139,955	180,842	204,211	32,128	1
Variance	124,695	139,706	184,476	29,891	166,110	172,599	182,079	7,984	1
Homogeneity	0,158	0,208	0,283	0,063	0,084	0,112	0,169	0,042	1
2x2	Close Up				Panoramic				H ¹
ASM ²	0,006	0,007	0,009	0,001	0,009	0,011	0,018	0,005	1
Contrast	85,074	136,638	140,856	27,891	105,684	136,397	143,832	19,074	0
Variance	125,172	130,199	136,844	5,836	87,974	113,140	125,218	18,622	1
Homogeneity	0,183	0,219	0,308	0,063	0,134	0,175	0,211	0,038	0
3x3	Close Up				Panoramic				H ¹
ASM ²	0,004	0,004	0,006	0,001	0,007	0,013	0,020	0,007	1
Contrast	92,940	109,503	126,276	16,668	216,033	398,403	563,231	173,599	1
Correlation	0,650	0,668	0,714	0,032	-0,025	0,093	0,255	0,140	1
Variance	149,790	175,832	187,880	19,045	208,010	247,728	319,437	55,713	1
Homogeneity	0,171	0,192	0,263	0,046	0,070	0,099	0,201	0,065	1
4x4	Close Up				Panoramic				H ¹
ASM ²	0,004	0,005	0,005	0,000	0,003	0,004	0,008	0,002	0
Contrast	14,371	22,420	36,517	11,073	46,921	59,129	63,910	8,495	1
Variance	123,588	130,785	149,769	13,091	199,076	214,980	228,864	14,894	1
Homogeneity	0,255	0,313	0,378	0,062	0,164	0,191	0,260	0,048	1
5x5	Close Up				Panoramic				H ¹
ASM ²	0,002	0,002	0,002	0,000	0,004	0,005	0,008	0,002	1
Contrast	66,575	73,495	83,820	8,623	69,632	73,727	127,037	28,702	0
Variance	352,274	361,911	443,552	45,639	99,908	129,627	148,866	24,479	1
Homogeneity	0,222	0,272	0,337	0,058	0,136	0,184	0,255	0,060	0
6x6	Close Up				Panoramic				H ¹
ASM ²	0,007	0,008	0,009	0,001	0,006	0,008	0,016	0,005	0
Contrast	5,460	19,888	82,026	38,283	19,614	39,627	88,315	34,351	0
Variance	53,806	67,104	91,228	18,711	39,854	66,280	84,479	22,313	0
Homogeneity	0,223	0,283	0,395	0,086	0,157	0,213	0,259	0,051	0
7x7	Close Up				Panoramic				H ¹
ASM ²	0,003	0,004	0,004	0,000	0,005	0,005	0,006	0,000	1
Contrast	9,823	34,718	37,989	14,083	145,387	183,663	211,423	33,018	1
Variance	116,088	128,013	132,280	8,096	142,879	158,957	165,295	11,208	1
Homogeneity	0,279	0,302	0,366	0,044	0,191	0,243	0,331	0,070	0
8x8	Close Up				Panoramic				H ¹
ASM ²	0,004	0,004	0,004	0,000	0,005	0,006	0,007	0,001	1
Contrast	146,746	177,348	219,807	36,531	182,898	192,621	205,115	11,108	0
Variance	209,670	222,585	263,742	27,036	140,551	185,740	231,379	45,414	0
Homogeneity	0,181	0,235	0,306	0,062	0,180	0,207	0,289	0,055	0
9x9	Close Up				Panoramic				H ¹
ASM ²	0,004	0,004	0,005	0,001	0,005	0,005	0,006	0,001	0
Contrast	92,847	134,650	217,301	62,227	152,685	275,657	340,813	94,064	0
Variance	274,098	281,545	355,591	40,746	241,219	266,176	310,354	34,568	0
Homogeneity	0,252	0,317	0,416	0,082	0,184	0,239	0,367	0,091	0
10x10	Close Up				Panoramic				H ¹
ASM ²	0,001	0,002	0,002	0,000	0,003	0,003	0,005	0,001	1
Contrast	458,211	474,857	497,588	19,688	117,432	135,803	170,820	26,694	1
Variance	466,977	530,053	635,333	84,178	147,640	164,110	180,763	16,562	1
Homogeneity	0,112	0,144	0,198	0,043	0,116	0,156	0,215	0,049	0

¹H IS THE RESULT OF WILCOXON RANK SUM TEST BETWEEN DIFFERENT VIEWING CONDITIONS WITH '1' INDICATING SIGNIFICANT DIFFERENCE, AND '0' NO SIGNIFICANT DIFFERENCE AT A=0.05

²ASM=ANGULAR SECOND MOMENT

TABLE II: SGLDM TEXTURE FEATURES (ANGLE1 – ANGLE2) FOR ALL SCALES {Q₁, Q₃, AND SIQR REPRESENT THE LOWER QUARTILE (25% PERCENTILE), UPPER QUARTILE (75% PERCENTILE) AND THE SEMI-INTER QUARTILE RANGE, RESPECTIVELY}

Scale	Q ₁	Median	Q ₃	SIQR	Q ₁	Median	Q ₃	SIQR	H ¹
1x1	Angle1				Angle2				
ASM ²	0,001	0,001	0,001	0,000	0,001	0,001	0,001	0,000	0
Contrast	149,712	254,531	356,072	103,180	118,712	304,900	321,611	101,450	0
Correlation	0,098	0,386	0,664	0,283	0,240	0,369	0,609	0,185	0
Variance	150,494	233,603	324,738	87,122	148,283	206,802	277,644	64,681	0
Homogeneity	0,061	0,073	0,098	0,018	0,064	0,075	0,107	0,021	0
2x2	Angle1				Angle2				H ¹
ASM ²	0,004	0,008	0,009	0,003	0,003	0,006	0,010	0,003	0
Contrast	3,226	5,200	28,449	12,612	3,781	7,423	25,429	10,824	0
Correlation	0,918	0,955	0,960	0,021	0,926	0,943	0,958	0,016	0
Variance	34,245	55,525	173,669	69,712	35,911	88,371	172,313	68,201	0
Homogeneity	0,296	0,428	0,487	0,096	0,323	0,442	0,461	0,069	0
3x3	Angle1				Angle2				
ASM ²	0,004	0,007	0,010	0,003	0,004	0,006	0,010	0,003	0
Contrast	3,914	6,167	43,625	19,855	4,645	6,110	21,942	8,648	0
Correlation	0,917	0,939	0,959	0,021	0,916	0,927	0,962	0,023	0
Variance	47,426	61,033	173,473	63,024	40,647	84,418	119,040	39,197	0
Homogeneity	0,266	0,406	0,469	0,101	0,295	0,401	0,478	0,091	0
4x4	Angle1				Angle2				H ¹
ASM ²	0,005	0,006	0,010	0,003	0,004	0,006	0,013	0,004	0
Contrast	4,223	11,416	74,508	35,142	9,113	13,238	29,496	10,192	0
Correlation	0,892	0,918	0,953	0,031	0,882	0,894	0,918	0,018	0
Variance	41,899	101,078	197,298	77,699	32,052	86,897	152,139	60,044	0
Homogeneity	0,207	0,318	0,437	0,115	0,240	0,317	0,467	0,113	0
5x5	Angle1				Angle2				H ¹
ASM ²	0,005	0,010	0,013	0,004	0,006	0,008	0,014	0,004	0
Contrast	5,840	8,701	94,390	44,275	5,770	15,584	33,272	13,751	0
Correlation	0,829	0,868	0,928	0,050	0,844	0,881	0,920	0,038	0
Variance	31,524	39,478	190,244	79,360	36,399	75,685	117,676	40,638	0
Homogeneity	0,177	0,352	0,402	0,112	0,239	0,297	0,430	0,095	0
10x10	Angle1				Angle2				H ¹
ASM ²	0,015	0,017	0,019	0,002	0,015	0,016	0,018	0,002	0
Contrast	15,561	24,612	248,969	116,704	19,120	37,065	104,593	42,737	0
Correlation	0,625	0,729	0,758	0,066	0,632	0,700	0,774	0,071	0
Variance	32,146	56,929	230,060	98,957	44,146	67,669	142,880	49,367	0
Homogeneity	0,114	0,212	0,252	0,069	0,145	0,200	0,232	0,044	0

¹H IS THE RESULT OF WILCOXON RANK SUM TEST BETWEEN DIFFERENT VIEWING CONDITIONS WITH '1' INDICATING SIGNIFICANT DIFFERENCE, AND '0' NO SIGNIFICANT DIFFERENCE AT A=0.05

²ASM=ANGULAR SECOND MOMENT

Also other texture features like the correlation showed that for the different distance viewing positions it is difficult to extract conclusions because of the variability of the correlation values with scale as illustrate in Fig 5.

The multiscale texture features ASM, contrast, variance and homogeneity for angle1 vs. angle2 views are tabulated in Table II for scales 1x1 to 5x5 and 10x10. As shown in Table II, for all scales all four features have no significant difference.

Figures 6 and 7 illustrate the multiscale analysis results for the second experiment (capturing under consecutive angle views) for the texture features homogeneity and entropy respectively. It is shown that these features have similar values for scales 2x2 up to 5x5. The same applies for their standard deviation values (Fig. 6c and 7c).

Figure 3: Multiscale analysis for homogeneity feature a) panoramic view, b) close up view, and c) standard deviation values.

Figure 4: Multiscale analysis for entropy feature a) panoramic view, b) close up view, and c) standard deviation values.

Figure 5: Multiscale analysis for correlation feature a) panoramic view, b) close up view, and c) standard deviation values.

Figure 6: Multiscale analysis for homogeneity feature a) angle 1 view, b) angle 2 view, and c) standard deviation values.

Figure 7: Multiscale analysis for entropy feature a) angle 1 view, b) angle 2 view, and c) standard deviation values.

4. Concluding Remarks

Results indicate that there is significant variability between the close up and panoramic views for multiscale texture features. However, there is some variance (within reasonable bounds) between the multiscale texture features of consecutive angles. It is hoped that the results of this study will prove useful in computer aided diagnosis in laparoscopy imaging. However, more experiments have to be carried out and more images have to be analyzed to support this further.

Acknowledgements

This study is funded through the Research Promotion Foundation, Cyprus, PENEK 2002, Program for the Financial Support of New Researchers, through the project entitled: *Integrated System for the Digital Analysis of Endoscopic Imaging Macrobiopsy for the Support of the Diagnosis of Gynaecological Cancer (IPPOKRATIS)*, December 2002 – December 2004.

References

- [1] Fayed J.A., Vogel M.F., 'Comparison of different treatment methods of endometriomas by laparoscopy', *Obstet. Gynecol.*, Vol. 78, pp. 660-665, 1991.
- [2] Wenzl R, Lehner R, Vry Uwe, Pateisky N, Sevelde P, Husslein P, 'Three-dimensional video-endoscopy: clinical use in gynaecological laparoscopy', *Lancet*, Vol. 344, pp. 1621-1622, 1994.
- [3] Karkanis S. A., Iakovidis D. K., Maroulis D. E., Karras Dimitris A., Tzivras M., 'Computer-aided tumor detection in endoscopic video using color wavelet features', *IEEE Transactions on Information Technology in Biomedicine*, Vol. 7(3), pp. 141-152, 2003.
- [4] Tjoa P. M., Krishnan M. S., 'Feature extraction for the analysis of colon status from the endoscopic images', *BioMedical Engineering OnLine*, Apr. 2003, <http://www.biomedical-engineering-online.com/content/2/1/9>.
- [5] Neophytou M.S., Pattichis C.S., Tanos V, Kyriacou E., Koutsouris D., 'Texture Characterization of Gynaecological Tissue in Endoscopy: Preliminary Findings', CD-ROM Proceedings of the 1st MEDINF International Conference on Medical Informatics & Engineering, 12-15 October, Craiova, Romania, 4 pages, 2003.
- [6] Vaidyanathan P.P., 'Multirate Systems and filter banks', New Jersey: PTR Prentice Hall, 1993.
- [7] Haralick R.M., Shanmugam K., Dinstein I., 'Texture Features for Image Classification', *IEEE Trans. on Systems, Man., and Cybernetics*, Vol. SMC-3, pp. 610-621, Nov. 1973.
- [8] Weszka J.S., Dyer C.R., Rosenfield A., 'A Comparative Study of Texture Measures for Terrain Classification', *IEEE Trans. on Systems, Man. & Cybern.*, Vol. SMC-6, pp 629-285, April 1976.